

ISic3561

I.Sicily inscription 3561

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Philosophiana

Place of origin (modern)

near Mazzarino

Provenance

tomb 11, western necropolis, Sofiana (37.31424, 14.29943)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Gela, Museo Archeologico

Regionale di Gela, inventory 38325

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337234

1. ΣΕΚΟ-

2. ὕδα.

3.

4. Οἰκουμε-

5. νία.

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 565495

PHI 337234

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2002.0614B

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 52.0910B

Brugnone, A. 2002. Le iscrizioni. In Bonacasa Carra, R.M., Panvini, R.(eds.), *La Sicilia centro-merdionale tra il II ed il VI sec. d.C.*. Caltanissetta. pp. 295-301. At 296-297 no.2B fig.3

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